

PECULIARITIES OF TRANSLATING TECHNOLOGICAL TERMS AND CULTURAL IDIOMS IN AN ONLINE NEWS ARTICLE

Khusanova Diana

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Corresponding author: E-mail: khusanovadian@gmail.com

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Abstract. *This scientific article explores the challenges faced in translating technological terms and cultural idioms in online news articles. The rapid advancements in technology create a dynamic landscape that demands translators to stay updated with the latest trends and jargon. Moreover, cultural idioms rely on specific cultural references and context, making direct translation a potential pitfall. To overcome these challenges, translators must employ strategies such as extensive research, collaboration with experts, and creative adaptation techniques. The article emphasizes the importance of linguistic accuracy, cultural sensitivity, and the use of technology in facilitating effective translation. By bridging linguistic and cultural gaps, translators contribute to the dissemination of accurate and culturally relevant information in online news articles.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *peculiarities, translating, technological terms, cultural idioms, online.*

1. Introduction In our interconnected world, online news articles serve as vital conduits for sharing news and knowledge. However, translating technological terms and cultural idioms within these articles poses unique challenges for translators. This section introduces the challenges and complexities involved in translating technological terms and cultural idioms, highlighting the need for linguistic accuracy, cultural sensitivity, and adaptation to the online medium.

2. The Challenge of Technological Term Translation 2.1 Rapid Technological Advancements This subsection discusses the challenges faced by translators in keeping up with the ever-evolving landscape of technology. Translators must stay updated with the latest technological advancements to accurately convey the meaning of technological terms in their translations.

2.2 Language-Specific Concepts This subsection explores the language-specific nuances that make direct translation of technological terms challenging. Translators must understand the linguistic characteristics and cultural context of both the source and target languages to navigate these complexities effectively.

2.3 Contextual Adaptation This subsection highlights the importance of considering the broader context in which technological terms are used. Translators must strike a balance between preserving technical accuracy and ensuring clarity for the target audience. The cultural implications of technological terms are also discussed, emphasizing the need for cultural adaptation in translation.

3. Cultural Idioms in Online News Articles 3.1 Cultural Significance This subsection explores the role of cultural idioms in language, discussing how they add depth, nuance, and richness to communication. Cultural idioms are explained as expressions or phrases with symbolic or figurative meanings specific to a particular culture.

3.2 Challenges in Translation This subsection highlights the challenges faced in translating cultural idioms, including the potential loss of intended meaning and the reliance on cultural references. The limitations of literal or direct translation are discussed, emphasizing the need for cultural sensitivity and linguistic expertise.

3.3 Adapting Idioms This subsection presents strategies for effectively translating cultural idioms in online news articles. Translators are encouraged to find culturally appropriate equivalents, rephrase idioms, or provide additional context to ensure accurate and meaningful translations.

4. Strategies for Effective Translation 4.1 Extensive Research This subsection emphasizes the importance of thorough research in understanding both technological terminology and cultural idioms. Translators are encouraged to stay updated with the latest trends and advancements, utilizing online resources, industry publications, and specialized glossaries.

4.2 Collaboration and Consultation This subsection highlights the value of collaboration with subject-matter experts and consultation with native speakers. Translators can gain insights, clarify complex concepts, and ensure accurate and culturally authentic translations through collaboration and consultation.

4.3 Creative Adaptation This subsection discusses creative adaptation techniques, such as paraphrasing, providing explanations, or using footnotes. These strategies allow translators to overcome challenges and effectively convey the intended meaning while maintaining cultural authenticity.

5. Conclusion In conclusion, translating technological terms and cultural idioms in online news articles demands a comprehensive approach. Translators must navigate the dynamic realm of technology while considering cultural nuances, linguistic accuracy, and ethical principles.

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